

From Archives to AI: Using Old Maps and Gazetteers to Improve the Geoparsing Capabilities of Large Language Models

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Summary

Large language models (LLMs) reveal new opportunities for automated geoparsing of text and speech data, facilitating the collection of spatial data in settings where map literacy is low. However, the geoparsing capability of LLMs depends on the coverage of its training data and consequently will not perform well in regions without detailed map data. This research demonstrates how computer vision techniques can be used with old maps and gazetteers as a complimentary data source to improve the geoparsing capability of LLMs, demonstrating how patient journeys can be extracted from interview transcripts collected in a Ugandan medical facility.

KEYWORDS: Geocoding, Computer Vision, Artificial Intelligence, Historic Maps, ChatGPT

1. Introduction

As part of a recent project exploring disability rehabilitation services in south-west Uganda, interviews were conducted to understand patient journeys through the healthcare system to reach prosthetic rehabilitation services (Ackers et al., 2025). To add geographical context, participants were asked to identify key locations (home location, injury site, healthcare centres) using a digital mapping interface, supported by the interviewer. Many participants had poor map literacy, which made finding named locations difficult and time consuming. Though the resulting geographical data provided a rich source of information about experiences in the Ugandan healthcare system, it is clear that alternative approaches requiring lower map literacy would be valuable in global health research settings such as this. Automated geoparsing technologies provide a promising solution but have been challenging to implement.

The rise of large language models (LLMs) offers a potential solution (Mansourian and Oucheikh, 2024). Place names can be easily identified and converted into coordinates (geocoded) through natural language queries and returned in a spatial format (e.g., GeoJSON), which can then be verified. The process is relatively fast and simple, minimising disruption to the interview. However, the geocoding performance of a LLM depends on the coverage of its training data. At present, online LLMs (e.g., ChatGPT, DeepSeek) are trained using publicly available datasets (e.g., OpenStreetMap, Geonames) and are updated infrequently. Datasets such as OpenStreetMap are known to have unequal coverage, with a dominance of data in higher income countries and urban areas (Huck et al., 2021; Watkinson et

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al., 2022). Locations falling outside of these criteria (e.g., a rural village in Uganda), are unlikely to be included and will be geocoded inaccurately.

Paper maps and gazetteers provide a potential source of place name data where others may not exist. For example, in Uganda, paper maps of the entire country exist at a 1:50,000 scale (see Huck et al., 2021) along with gazetteers that were produced in the 1960’s by the UK Department for Colonial Surveys and the US Department of the Interior. Though outdated, the documents are a substantial dataset of place names. Paper maps and gazetteers can be scanned, georeferenced (maps), and used with computer vision (CV) to extract place names and their coordinates. The data can then be provided to a LLM and incorporated into its existing gazetteer to improve geoparsing performance.

Here, we demonstrate the usefulness of (old**) paper gazetteers and maps as a source of place name data. We perform tests to assess an LLM’s existing geoparsing performance (with plans to assess another LLM) using interviews collected in south-western Uganda in 2024. We then describe a method of place name and coordinate extraction from a paper gazetteer. Performance tests are planned to be repeated, to evaluate improvements in geoparsing performance and usefulness of the proposed method.

2. Methods

2.1 Geoparsing performance tests

For each interview transcript, personally identifiable information was removed. Transcripts were provided to ChatGPT alongside the query: “Can you identify the place names in this text and provide the coordinates in GeoJSON format?”. The GeoJSON was saved and loaded into QGIS. Any geoparsed locations that could not be geocoded were marked N/A. The distance between the geoparsed location and the location identified during the interview was then calculated.

2.2 Place name extraction

A digital version of the United States Official Standard Names of Uganda (Gazetteer 82, 1964) was downloaded and each page converted to image format. The gazetteer contains an alphabetical list of place names, their geographical designation, coordinate location, administrative area reference and map reference (**Figure 1**).

BUGERA	PPL	0 04 N	32 17 E	56709	01
BUGERA	PPL	0 55 S	31 43 E	56709	01
BUGERA	HLL	0 56 S	31 43 E	56709	01
BUGERE	PPL	0 34 S	31 41 E	56709	01
BUGERE	HLL	0 41 S	31 33 E	56709	02

Figure 1 Section of the gazetteer with named places and associated information. Here PPL is populated place and HLL is hill

Text recognition was performed in Python 3.12 using CV libraries OpenCV and PyTesseract. Each page was divided into two (separating the two columns of text) and a dilation filter applied. Text and numerical characters were then identified alongside their bounding areas (**Figure 2**). Using the value of the top bounding edge, characters on the same line were identified and combined into words using character spacing rules. Only lines containing the word ‘PPL’ (populated place) were further processed. The coordinate values for each place were identified in each line and added to a Pandas data frame

** Old maps refers to maps produced before the present-day. They differ from “historical maps”, which are new maps presenting historical data (Harper, 2018)

alongside place name. The final data frame is exported as a GeoJSON file. The workflow is summarised in **Figure 3**.

Figure 2 Character recognition using PyTesseract.

Figure 3 Text detection workflow.

2.3 LLM re-training, repeat performance tests and route construction

The resulting GeoJSON dataset can be used to inform the geoparsing process in an LLM. This ongoing work will repeat the geoparsing performance tests, comparing the gazetteer-derived locations to the interviewee identified locations; and assessing the impact of adding the gazetteer dataset to the LLM. The locations will then be verified by the original interview team and used to reconstruct routes to visualise patient journeys through the Ugandan healthcare system (e.g., **Figure 4**). Ongoing work will also evaluate the geoparsing performance of the newly released DeepSeek.

Figure 4 Expected output created through the connection of geoparsed locations to show patient journeys through the Ugandan healthcare system.

3. Results

Before providing the gazetteer dataset, ChatGPT identified 91 place names and coordinates from 12 interview transcripts. 26 were removed as repeats or places used when describing another location. Of the remaining 65 place names, distance between geolocated (by ChatGPT) and known location varied widely (**Figure 5**). The minimum distance was 745 m and maximum 185,761 m, with most differences measuring between 3,388 and 62,637 m. Spatially, higher differences in geolocated and known locations were observed in less populated areas, with smaller differences observed around cities (**Figure 6**). An oral presentation will compare the results presented here to in-progress analysis following the addition of the gazetteer dataset to ChatGPT (and DeepSeek).

Figure 5 Measured difference between ChatGPT geoparsed location and known locations.

Figure 6 Spatial patterns of measured difference between geolocated (ChatGPT) and known locations.

4. Discussion and conclusions

LLMs can offer an easy-to-use interface to automate geoparsing, with the potential to enable simple geographical contextualisation of research. However, the geoparsing performance of LLMs depends on the geographical coverage of their training data, making them challenging to implement in regions with poor map coverage (Huck et al., 2021; Watkinson et al., 2023, 2022). In this paper, we demonstrated the potential of old maps and gazetteers to fill current gaps in LLM coverage and presented a method for CV-based text detection of a paper gazetteer which can be used to “re-train” the LLM. Tests revealed varied geoparsing performance by ChatGPT (before re-training), with large differences between geolocated (ChatGPT) and known locations likely to be locations ChatGPT could not geocode due to missing data and simply generated a best guess in its place. Spatial patterns of geoparsing performance are as expected, with better performance in urban areas where the coverage of datasets such as OpenStreetMap are known to be higher (Watkinson et al., 2022; 2023).

Alongside limitations of LLMs, it is important to consider that old maps and gazetteers are outdated and may not contain all current named places. The maps and gazetteers considered in this work were produced shortly after Uganda’s period as a Protectorate of the British Empire and therefore are reflective of the interests of the Protectorate and their understandings of the environment (Edney, 1993). Consequently, the documents may not capture all named locations and names may vary from indigenous languages (Mbenzi, 2019). Old maps and gazetteers should therefore be viewed as complimentary to other methods of generating place name data (e.g., contributions to OpenStreetMap, local sources of information), which can be used together to improve the performance of LLMs and their automated geoparsing capabilities.

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